

Direct numerical simulation of a turbulent methane/air flame impinged by a sub-breakdown electric field

Mario Di Renzo^{a,b,*}, Bénédicte Cuenot^a

^aCentre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique, Toulouse 31100, France

^bCenter for Turbulence Research, Stanford University, CA, 94305, USA

Abstract

The effects of an external electric field on a turbulent methane/air diffusion flame are analyzed in this work using direct numerical simulations. The analyzed configuration consists of a temporally evolving mixing layer of air and a mixture of methane and nitrogen at 1 atm that is impinged by an electric field in the direction normal to the mean mixing plane. The combustion and chemi-ionization reactions involved in the flow are modeled using finite-rate chemistry and a reduced reaction scheme consisting of 26 species and 134 reactions. The mass diffusion and ion-wind effects are modeled using a detailed description of the diffusion coefficients and electric mobilities based on kinetic theory. The presented calculations show that the turbulence generated within the mixing layer is mostly unaffected by the applied electric field for the configuration under exam. In fact, the electric body force is developed away from the mixing region where the flow is uniform. Conversely, the turbulence is able to introduce very high intermittency in the electrically charged species concentration and, consequently, in the electric body force. Such intermittency will constitute a challenge in the future formulation of combustion models that take into account ion-wind effects.

Keywords: Diffusion flames, Sub-breakdown electric-fields, Turbulent mixing layer, Electric drift, Chemi-ionization.

1. Introduction

The first experiments that demonstrated the potential of using sub-breakdown electric fields to control many aspects of hydrocarbon combustion date back to 1931 [1, 2]. After those experiments, many studies have investigated multiple aspects of the interaction of electric fields and flames. For instance, Kim *et al.* [3, 4] have shown that low-frequency alternating current (AC) electric fields are able to stabilise premixed Bunsen flames. Park *et al.* [5] reduced soot formation in counterflow burner flames using direct current (DC) electric fields. Volkov *et al.* [6] demonstrated the ability of DC electric fields to control thermoacoustic instabilities, at least in a specific range of frequencies. Moreover, applying electric fields has enabled a significant reduction in the liftoff height of lifted flames [7, 8]. Similarly, augmentation of the flame propagation speed has been observed for premixed flames subjected to DC [9] and AC [10] electric fields. Benefits in applying external electric fields have even been demonstrated in combustion of liquid fuels, whereby the difference of potential was able to promote secondary atomization and influence the drop motion [11, 12].

Despite the number of experimental pieces of evidence collected over the years, the number of numerical studies

about electrified flames is limited. Specifically, the very high numerical stiffness associated with the integration of the ion motion and particularly of free electrons has complicated the numerical investigations. Most of the efforts are related to one-dimensional premixed flames. This setup is the most amenable to numerical studies because it requires the least number of degrees of freedom to be described. However, this numerical configuration is not informative of the coupling between electric and hydrodynamic fields because the electric body forces are irrotational, therefore their effects are completely absorbed by the hydrodynamic pressure field. These one-dimensional setups have been mainly utilized to perform fundamental studies about the flame/electric-field interaction [13–16] and to develop chemical mechanisms and transport models [17, 18]. Prager *et al.* [19] presented one of the first examples of a computational framework able to describe the transport of charged species within premixed flames without any external electric field. The first numerical framework that considers multi-component mixtures with complex transport and includes effects of external electric fields was instead proposed by Speelman *et al.* [20, 21].

Increasing the dimensionality of flames generates a much more interesting scenario from a fluid-dynamic standpoint. In fact, the electric body force is not guaranteed to be irrotational in two- and three-dimensional configurations. Consequently, the applied electric field is capable of inducing vorticity and modify the flow around the flame. On the other hand, the numerical integration of multi-dimensional

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: mario.direnzo@cerfacs.fr (Mario Di Renzo), cuenot@cerfacs.fr (Bénédicte Cuenot)

electrified flames becomes significantly more challenging because of the increase in degrees of freedom in the numerical solution [22]. Yamashita *et al.* [23] were among the first researchers to investigate a two-dimensional electrified flame. They carried out an experimental/numerical study whereby a capillary methane/air diffusion flame was interacting with an external electric field oriented in the same direction as gravity. They showed that the applied electric field was able to completely counteract and sometimes prevail buoyancy of the burnt gasses. In this study, the numerical stiffness of the problem was palliated by deploying a reduced chemical mechanism and an implicit iterative method. Other studies related to two-dimensional configurations were carried out on lifted planar-jet flames [24–26]. These studies utilized Flamelet Progress Variable (FPV) models modified to describe the combustion chemionization chemistry while retaining an acceptable computational cost. The main outcome of these contributions was a deeper understanding of the physical mechanism that induces the reduction of the lift-off height of jet flames. Direct numerical simulations of axisymmetric laminar counterflow diffusion flames have been performed only very recently [27–29]. These calculations highlighted a two-way-coupled interaction between the electric body force and the flame, whereby the electric body force reduces the overall strain rate of the flow which, in turn, makes the chemistry increasingly faster and reduces the amount of charged species produced by the flame. Recently, a three-dimensional calculation of Bunsen flame impinged by a traverse electric field was carried out by Belhi *et al.* [30]. This study showed that direct numerical simulations executed using reduced chemistry mechanisms are capable of, at least qualitatively, reproducing the experimental distortion of the flame shape introduced by the electric field.

A thorough characterization of the interaction between electrified flames and turbulence is still required to formulate predictive models. This manuscript aims at providing a first description of an electrified turbulent flame. Considering the richness of the flow physics and the numerical complexity associated with the accurate prediction of this interaction, this study is carried out in a simple geometric configuration. Temporally and spatially evolving mixing layers have traditionally been among the most common configurations to study fundamental problems related to combustion [31–37]. In particular, a temporally evolving mixing layer will be considered in this study in view of its reduced computational complexity due to the presence of two statistically homogeneous directions. After a description of the modeling choices, numerical methods, and flow configuration utilized in this work, the rest of the manuscript will be focused on answering three main research questions: i) what are the effects of turbulence on the electrically charged species produced by the flame and on their transport? ii) is the ion wind capable of modifying the main turbulence statistics of the flow? iii) are electrified flames amenable for turbulent FPV models and

Figure 1: Schematics of the computational setup considered in this study.

what are the most challenging terms that will need to be closed?

2. Computational setup

A methane/air diffusion flame embedded in a temporal mixing layer is numerically studied in this work. The numerical setup schematized in Figure 1 consists of a cuboidal domain in a physical space $\mathbf{x} = [x, y, z]$ where two streams of fuel and oxidizer at pressure $P_r = 1 \text{ atm}$ flow in opposite directions, mix and react. The oxidizer flow is composed of standard dry air while the fuel flow is a mixture of methane and nitrogen. The composition of the fuel flow is approximately 36% of methane and 64% of N_2 , on a molar basis, and is determined such that the stoichiometric mixture fraction is $Z_{st} = 0.2$. This value of the stoichiometric mixture fraction is a compromise between considering a pure methane fuel stream, which is more relevant for industrial applications, and positioning the flame in the proximity of the shear layer, where turbulence is formed. Moreover, this Z_{st} has been chosen in analogy with previous studies available in the literature and warrants an interaction between the flame and the turbulence [35]. The temperature of the air stream is $T_a = 300 \text{ K}$, whereas the fuel is at about 365 K , which ensures that the two streams are at the same density. The fuel and air streams flow along the x direction at velocities equal to $-\Delta U/2$ and $\Delta U/2$, respectively. This numerical setup is representative of a spatial mixing layer developing between two parallel mesh electrodes, which are utilized to impose the external electric field. The value of ΔU is set using the convective Mach number $Ma_c = \Delta U / (c_f + c_a) = 0.025$, where c_f and c_a are the speed of sound in the fuel and air mixture, respectively. The reason behind the choice of such a low convective Mach number is discussed later in Sec. 4. An external sub-breakdown electric field E^0 is applied along

the y direction to steer the charged species naturally produced by the flame. The intensity of the applied electric field is determined by imposing the interaction parameter

$$\Xi = \frac{\epsilon_0}{\rho_r} \left(\frac{E^0}{\Delta U} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

which measures the ratio between the characteristic electric body forces and the convective acceleration of the flow [27, 28]. The symbol ϵ_0 in Eq. (1) is the dielectric permeability of vacuum while ρ_r is the reference density, chosen as that of the air stream. The calculations discussed in this work are executed considering $\Xi = 10^{-2}$, which produces a reduced electric field $E/N < 50\text{Td}$ everywhere in the computational domain. In the reduced electric field expression, $N = \rho N_A / \bar{W}$ is the number density of the gas mixture, N_A is the Avogadro number, ρ is the local mixture density, and \bar{W} is the local mean molar mass of the gas. This upper bound of the reduced electric field suggests that thermal non-equilibrium effects will have a negligible role in the flow under exam [38].

The evolution of the described flow is computed in this work by solving the transport equations of species partial densities, momentum, and total energy, namely

$$\frac{\partial(\rho Y_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho Y_i \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla \cdot (\rho Y_i \mathbf{V}_i) + \dot{w}_i \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, N_s, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla P + \nabla \cdot \bar{\bar{\tau}} + \rho_q \mathbf{E}, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\rho e_0)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} h_0) = & \nabla \cdot \left(\lambda \nabla T + \bar{\bar{\tau}} \mathbf{u} - \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \rho_i \mathbf{V}_i h_i \right) \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \rho_{q,i} (\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{V}_i) \cdot \mathbf{E}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In the previous equations, t is the time coordinate, Y_i is the mass fraction of the i -th species, N_s is the number of considered chemical species, $\mathbf{u} = [u, v, w]$ is the flow velocity vector, and P is the thermodynamic pressure. The symbol $\bar{\bar{\tau}}$ denotes the viscous stress tensor

$$\bar{\bar{\tau}} = \sigma \left[\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T - 2(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}}/3 \right], \quad (5)$$

where σ is the dynamic viscosity of the mixture evaluated composing the dynamic viscosity of each species using the Wilke's rule [39]. In Eq. (5), the symbol $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}}$ is the identity tensor.

The specific total energy of the gas mixture is defined as $e_0 = e + |\mathbf{u}|^2/2$, whereby e is the specific internal energy, namely

$$e = h - P/\rho = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} Y_i h_i - P/\rho. \quad (6)$$

In the previous expressions, $h_0 = h + |\mathbf{u}|^2/2$ is the specific stagnation enthalpy, h is the specific enthalpy of the mixture, and h_i is the partial specific enthalpy of species i given by

$$h_i = h_{i,\text{ref}} + \int_{T_{\text{ref}}}^T c_{p,i}(T') dT', \quad (7)$$

where $h_{i,\text{ref}}$ is a reference value of the specific enthalpy at the reference temperature T_{ref} . In Eq. 7, $c_{p,i}$ is a temperature-dependent specific heat capacity of species i at constant pressure, which is evaluated using the NASA polynomials [40, 41]. In Eq. (4), λ is the thermal conductivity of the mixture and it is computed by averaging the local thermal conductivities of each species [42].

The diffusion velocity vector \mathbf{V}_i for the weakly ionized gas considered in this work is defined as

$$\mathbf{V}_i = -D_i \nabla (\ln X_i) - \mathcal{S}_i \mu_i \nabla \Phi + \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} Y_j [D_j \nabla (\ln X_j) + \mathcal{S}_j \mu_j \nabla \Phi], \quad (8)$$

whereby the first two terms on the right-hand side (RHS) correspond to the mass diffusion [43] and the electric field induced ion wind [44], respectively. The third term is a mass corrector that ensures the conservation of mass [45, 46]. From a numerical point of view, the mass corrector for the electric drift is negligible with respect to the other terms because the ionized species mass fractions are always lower than 10^{-8} in the considered conditions. In this formulation, X_i , μ_i , and D_i are the molar fraction, the electric mobility, and the mass diffusivity of species i , respectively. The mass diffusivities and electric mobilities are computed by weighting the individual binary diffusivities and mobilities of the mixture components as in Ref. [47, 48]. The binary transport properties of the neutral species and heavy ions are computed using the Stockmayer potential [49] and the (n,6,4) theory [50], respectively. The electric mobility of the free-electron μ_{e^-} is equal to $0.2 \text{ m}^2/(\text{s V})$ while their mass diffusivity D_{e^-} is computed with the Einstein relation $D_{e^-} = (k_B \mu_{e^-} T) / e_c$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and $e_c = 1.60218 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$ is the elementary electric charge value. \mathcal{S}_i is the number of elementary charges of the i -th species ($\mathcal{S}_i = 0$ for neutral species, $\mathcal{S}_i > 0$ for positive ions, and $\mathcal{S}_i < 0$ for negative ions and electrons). The value of μ_{e^-} utilized in these calculations was determined during the derivation of the considered chemical mechanism [51]. The metric utilized for determining μ_{e^-} was the agreement with ion-current saturation voltage experimentally measured by Speelman *et al.* [20]. The charged species transport could probably be improved by a more accurate model for the electric mobility of the free-electrons [52], though the results presented in the rest of the manuscript will most likely be unaffected by such variation of the formulation as long as the drift velocity of the free-electrons remains much larger than all the other characteristic velocities of the flow.

The equation of state for a multicomponent mixture of

ideal gases,

$$P = \rho R^0 T / \bar{W}, \quad (9)$$

is utilized as a constitutive relation. In the previous expression, R^0 is the universal gas constant and $\bar{W} = (\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} Y_i / W_i)^{-1}$ is the mean molar mass based on the individual weights W_i of each species.

The last terms on the RHS of Eqs. (3) and (4) represent the electric body force and the Joule dissipation. These terms are computed using the local electric field $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\Phi$, where Φ is the local electrostatic potential evaluated using the Gauss law

$$\epsilon_0 \nabla^2 \Phi + \rho_q = 0, \quad (10)$$

and ρ_q is the electric charge density of the mixture. The latter is obtained by the summation of the partial electric charge densities of each species, namely

$$\rho_q = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \rho_{q,i} = \rho N_A e_c \frac{S_i Y_i}{W_i}. \quad (11)$$

The chemical production rates \dot{w}_i in Eq. (2) are based on the reaction mechanism presented in Ref. [51]. This mechanism considers 26 species, which react through 134 reactions. These species include two positive ions (HCO^+ and H_3O^+), one negative ion (O_2^-), and the free-electrons. At the same time, N_2 , which is by far the most abundant species in this setup, is inert. The accuracy of this reduced mechanism has been assessed by comparing its results with the experimental data of Speelman *et al.* [21]. A list of all the species and reactions included in the mechanisms, along with their model coefficients, are included in the supplementary material of Ref. [51].

The described equations are numerically integrated in a cuboidal domain whose size is $31\delta_\omega^0 \times 20\delta_\omega^0 \times 8\delta_\omega^0$ in the streamwise, mixing, and spanwise directions, respectively. δ_ω^0 is the vorticity thickness $\delta_\omega = \Delta U / (\partial \bar{u} / \partial y)_{max}$ computed at the initial condition of the calculation. A Cartesian computational grid composed of $768 \times 384 \times 192$ points is utilized to discretize the transport equations. Uniform spacing is utilized in the streamwise and spanwise directions while a hyperbolic sine stretching is deployed in the y -direction to cluster the points close to the reacting region of the flow. A sixth-order skew-symmetric scheme, that discretely preserves kinetic energy, is utilized for the Euler fluxes [53]. A second-order central scheme is utilized for the discretization of the diffusion fluxes and of the Gauss law. Finally, the drift fluxes of the charged species are treated using a TENO6 scheme [54]. The resulting system of ordinary differential equations is integrated in time using a third order strong stability preserving Runge–Kutta scheme [55]. The calculations presented in this work are carried out with the described numerical procedure in the Hypersonic Task-based Research (HTR) solver [56–58]. The HTR solver leverages the runtime Legion [59–61] and the programming language Regent [62] to execute the described calculations on high-performance supercomputers

with heterogeneous architectures. Specifically, the supercomputing facility Lassen at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) has been utilized in the present work. Further details of the physics and numerical formulation of the HTR solver are provided in Ref. [56, 58, 63] along with several verification tests. In particular, Ref. [58] provides a comparison of the results of the HTR solver with the open-source solver CANTERA [64] for the one-dimensional electrified flames.

The boundary conditions for the fluid dynamics of the presented calculations are periodic in the x and z directions while the surfaces normal to the y direction are treated with a one-dimensional non-reflecting outflow boundary conditions [65, 66]. The electric potential is imposed on the outflow surfaces using a Robin boundary condition that imposes only the mean value of the electric potential and extrapolates the oscillations from the interior of the computational domain. Specifically, the mean value of Φ is set to zero at $y = -10\delta_\omega^0$ and to $-E^0 L_y$ at $y = 10\delta_\omega^0$. The boundary conditions for the charged species mass fractions are imposed to zero in case the charged particle is repelled from the non-periodic boundary to avoid spurious injections of ions. On the other hand, zero normal-gradient conditions of the mass fraction are imposed where the charged species flows toward the non-periodic boundary. Note that the flow configuration considered in this work is independent of the size of the computational domain L_y . Considering that the current density produced by the flame $J = \rho N_A e_c E_y \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} S_i Y_i \mu_i / W_i = \rho_q E_y \bar{\mu}$ is constant outside the mixing layer for the charge conservation principle, the Gauss law can be rewritten as

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left[\left(\frac{d\Phi}{dy} \right)^2 \right] = \frac{2J}{\bar{\mu}\epsilon_0}, \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\mu} = (S_i Y_i \mu_i / W_i) / (S_i Y_i / W_i)$ is the species averaged electric mobility. This equation can be analytically integrated outside the mixing layer to provide the additional electric potential difference that needs to be added to the baseline voltage to extend the domain.

The presented calculations are initialized with the initial condition detailed in Sec. 2.1. The flow is then left free to evolve without any applied electric field. In this way, the initial transition to turbulence is achieved in a more computationally efficient manner. Once a linear growth of the shear layer momentum thickness is observed, the electric field is applied.

In this formulation, the overbar $\overline{(\cdot)}$ denotes the Reynolds averaging operator in the periodic directions (x, z) whereas the tilde $\widetilde{(\cdot)}$ is the Favre averaging operator, defined for a generic quantity ϕ as $\widetilde{\phi} = \overline{\rho\phi} / \bar{\rho}$. The fluctuations around the Reynolds average are defined as $\phi' = \phi - \bar{\phi}$ while the Favre fluctuations are $\phi'' = \phi - \widetilde{\phi}$.

2.1. Initial conditions

At the beginning of the calculation ($t = 0$), the x component of the velocity vector is set to a hyperbolic tangent

profile $u^0(y) = \Delta U/2 \tanh(-y/\delta_U)$, where the parameter δ_U is utilized to set the thickness of the shear layer. In particular, δ_U is chosen to enforce an initial Reynolds number $Re_\omega^0 = \rho_r \delta_\omega^0 \Delta U / \sigma_r = 5500$, where σ_r is the reference dynamic viscosity which is defined equal to the dynamic viscosity of the air stream. A random isotropic turbulence velocity signal with an amplitude equal to $0.05\Delta U$ and energy spectrum

$$E(k) = (k/k_0)^4 \exp\left[-2(k/k_0)^2\right] \quad (13)$$

is superimposed to the mean velocity field to promote the transition to turbulence. In Eq. (13), k is the wavenumber and $k_0 = 10$ is the energy-peak wave number. This random velocity signal is modulated with an exponential function $e^{-[y/(4\delta_\omega^0)]^2}$ to damp the disturbances away from the shear layer.

The thermochemical state of the two streams is initialized starting from a mixture fraction field defined with a hyperbolic tangent profile $Z^0(y) = (1 + \tanh(y/\delta_z))/2$ with δ_z determined such that the normalized stoichiometric scalar dissipation rate $\chi_{st}^0 \delta_\omega^0 / \Delta U = 2D_{T,st}^0 |\nabla Z^0|^2 \delta_\omega^0 / \Delta U = 5 \times 10^{-3}$. $D_{T,st}^0 = \lambda_{st}^0 / (\rho_{st}^0 c_{p,st}^0)$ is the thermal diffusivity of the stoichiometric mixture at the initial conditions. The thermochemical state of the mixture is then determined as function of the mixture fraction field. In particular, the pressure is set equal to P_r and if the local mixture fraction is lower than the stoichiometric value, the gas composition and temperature are

$$Y_i = Y_{i,a} + (Y_{i,eq} - Y_{i,a}) \frac{Z}{Z_{st}} \quad (14)$$

and

$$T = T_a + (T_{eq} - T_a) \frac{Z}{Z_{st}}, \quad (15)$$

otherwise they are

$$Y_i = Y_{i,eq} + (Y_{i,f} - Y_{i,eq}) \frac{Z - Z_{st}}{1 - Z_{st}} \quad (16)$$

and

$$T = T_{eq} + (T_f - T_{eq}) \frac{Z - Z_{st}}{1 - Z_{st}}. \quad (17)$$

In the above expressions, the subscripts f and a mean that the quantity is evaluated in the fuel and air stream, respectively, whereas the eq subscript means that the quantity is evaluated in the burnt equilibrium state of the stoichiometric mixture.

3. Structure of the electroneutral flame

This section contains an analysis of two main non-electrified states of the described mixing layer. These two states, which will be named “lo-Re” and “hi-Re”, are utilized as starting points for the electrified calculations that will be analyzed in the next sections of this work. The state “lo-Re” is selected at the beginning of the linear

Case	lo-Re	hi-Re
Re_ω	6980	10460
Re_θ	844	1062
$Re_\lambda _{y=0}$	39	43
$\frac{\Delta_i}{\eta} _{y=-\delta_\omega/2}$	[0.96, 0.37, 0.99]	[1.06, 0.55, 1.09]
$\frac{\Delta_i}{\eta} _{y=0}$	[1.16, 0.22, 1.20]	[1.20, 0.23, 1.24]
$\frac{\Delta_i}{\eta} _{y=\delta_\omega/2}$	[1.66, 0.63, 1.71]	[1.76, 0.92, 1.82]
$\frac{\ell_1}{L_x} _{y=-\delta_\omega/2}$	0.044	0.040
$\frac{\ell_1}{L_x} _{y=0}$	0.055	0.059
$\frac{\ell_1}{L_x} _{y=\delta_\omega/2}$	0.035	0.026
$\frac{\ell_3}{L_z} _{y=-\delta_\omega/2}$	0.042	0.043
$\frac{\ell_3}{L_z} _{y=0}$	0.041	0.037
$\frac{\ell_3}{L_z} _{y=\delta_\omega/2}$	0.039	0.036

Table 1: Summary of the main dimensionless and numerical parameters of the electroneutral mixing layer analysed in Sec. 3. In the table, Re_ω , Re_θ , and Re_λ are the Reynolds numbers based on the vorticity thickness, momentum thickness, and Taylor microscale, respectively. Moreover, Δ_i indicates the grid spacing in the Cartesian directions, η is the local Kolmogorov length scale, and ℓ_1 and ℓ_3 are the integral length scales associated to the streamwise velocity in the streamwise and spanwise directions, respectively.

growth of the mixing layer momentum thickness, whereas the state “hi-Re” corresponds to later stages of the flow evolution. The Reynolds numbers based on the vorticity thickness differ among the two states for a factor of about 1.5. The main dimensionless parameters that characterize the physical and numerical states of the mixing layer in the two selected time instants are summarized in Table 1. In particular, the table reports the Reynolds number based on the momentum thickness $Re_\theta = \rho_r \delta_\theta \Delta U / \sigma_r$, whereby the momentum thickness δ_θ is defined as

$$\delta_\theta = \frac{1}{\rho_r (\Delta U)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{\rho} \left(\frac{\Delta U}{2} - \tilde{u} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta U}{2} + \tilde{u} \right) dy. \quad (18)$$

The Reynolds number based on the Taylor microscale is computed on the centerline of the domain ($y = 0$) as $Re_\lambda = 2\tilde{k}\sqrt{5}/(\bar{\nu}\bar{\epsilon})$, where $\tilde{k} = \widetilde{u_i''u_i''}/2$ is the turbulent kinetic energy, $\nu = \sigma/\rho$ is the kinematic viscosity, and $\bar{\epsilon} = \overline{\tau_{ij}\partial u_i''/\partial x_j}/\bar{\rho}$ is the turbulent dissipation rate. The quoted integral scales are instead based on the streamwise velocity and are computed as $\ell_i = (1/\bar{u}^2) \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u_i(\mathbf{x})u_i(\mathbf{x} + e_i r) dr$ where $i = 1, 3$ and e_i is the unit vector oriented in the Cartesian direction i . Note the measured Δ_i/η ensures a resolution appropriate for a direct numerical simulation and the values of ℓ_1/L_x and ℓ_3/L_z warrant a sufficient decorrelation of the flow field in the periodic directions.

Figure 2 shows the profiles of Favre-averaged streamwise velocity, turbulent kinetic energy, Reynolds-averaged density mean and root-mean-squared (RMS) obtained at the “lo-Re” and “hi-Re” states. The four panels shown in the figure display a remarkable similarity among the profiles for these fluid dynamic quantities. This aspect of the two solutions analyzed in this section highlights the appropriateness of the y/δ_θ as self-similar variable in the

Figure 2: Profiles of Favre-averaged (a) streamwise velocity, (b) turbulent kinetic energy, Reynolds-averaged density (c) mean, and (d) RMS plotted for two different instantaneous solutions of the mixing layer. The continuous and dashed lines correspond to the solutions at lower and higher Reynolds number, respectively. The mixing normal direction is normalized by the instantaneous mixing layer momentum thickness and only a portion of the computational domain is plotted.

description of the mixing layer evolution even in this reacting case [67, 68]. The minor differences between the two sets of profiles, which are mainly visible in density RMS plot and at the peak of \bar{k} , are attributed to oscillations in the spatial averages due to the finite size of the computational domain rather than to effective differences in the mixing layer structure.

Some key quantities of the neutral chemistry fields extracted in the “lo-Re” and “hi-Re” states are reported in Figure 3. Figure 3(a) shows the Favre averaged mean distribution of the Bilger mixture fraction [69], which is defined as

$$Z = \frac{Z_C/(\nu_C W_C) + Z_H/(\nu_H W_H) + 2(Z_{O,a} - Z_O)/(\nu_O W_O)}{Z_{C,f}/(\nu_C W_C) + Z_{H,f}/(\nu_H W_H) + 2Z_{O,a}/(\nu_O W_O)}, \quad (19)$$

where Z_i are the element mass fractions and ν_C , ν_H , and ν_O are the stoichiometric coefficients of the global elemental reaction written as

The species mixing layer is similar on average in the two shear layer states analyzed in this section. On the other hand, differences in the mixing process emerge when analyzing the fluctuation-based scalar dissipation rate defined as

$$\widetilde{\chi''^2} = 2 \frac{\lambda}{\rho \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} c_{p,i}} |\nabla Z''|^2, \quad (21)$$

plotted in figure 3(b). Even though the width of $\widetilde{\chi''^2}$ is similar in the two plotted profiles, “hi-Re” exhibits a higher peak of normalized scalar dissipation rate. In fact, while

Figure 3: Profiles of (a) Favre-averaged Bilger mixture fraction, (b) mean scalar dissipation rate, and the (c) mean and (d) RMS of Reynolds-averaged molar fraction of some of the main species involved in the combustion process. The continuous and dashed lines correspond to the solutions at lower and higher Reynolds number, respectively. The mixing normal direction is normalized by the instantaneous mixing layer momentum thickness and only a portion of the computational domain is plotted. The profiles corresponding to CH have been magnified in panels (c) and (d).

the mixing layer thickens as the calculation progresses, the average species gradients and diffusion fluxes decrease their magnitude. Having a higher peak in figure 3(b) for the “hi-Re” state means that the species diffusion fluxes are not well scaled by the momentum thickness and that non-linear turbulence effects are able to partially recover the decrease of the species mixing due to the mixing layer growth.

The distributions of first and second-order statistics for some key species molar fractions are shown in Figure 3(c,d). In analogy to the observations made for the mixture fraction field, the composition mixing layer appears to be well-scaled by the momentum thickness. The mean profiles of fuel, oxidizer, and main products of the combustion process (CO_2 and H_2O) are indistinguishable

in the two states. Similarly, the Favre RMS of these species molar fractions have very similar distributions in the mixing layer. The minor discrepancies observed between the two sets of profiles are mostly within plotting accuracy and are attributed to a lack of statistical convergence in the spatial averages. The statistics of CH molar fractions are presented together with the other major components of the mixture. Even though CH is present in very low concentrations ($X_{CH} \ll 1$) in the computational domain, this radical is central to the chemi-ionization process happening in the reacting layer of the flame. Figure 3(c) shows that the state “hi-Re” has a lower peak of CH on average. In fact, this mixing layer state has a lower scalar dissipation rate and therefore a chemistry that is overall faster than the diffusion fluxes. For this reason, a lower

concentration of intermediate species as CH is found in the mixture. Conversely, the magnitude of the CH molar fraction fluctuations is similar in the two analyzed states, pointing at higher relative intermittency of the radical molar fraction field.

4. Effects of electric body force on the mean flow

The effects of the electric body force on the evolution of the mean flow around the turbulent flame are analyzed in this section. The discussed results are obtained by applying the external electric field starting from the “lo-Re” and “hi-Re” conditions. The two electrified calculations are advanced in time for about $20\delta_\theta^0/\Delta U$ and are labeled “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re” and “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re”. After the application of the external electric field, the charged species distribution undergoes a transient due to the introduction of the electric-field-induced flux. This transient lasts for about $3\delta_\theta^0/\Delta U$. The attention is focused on the effects of the electric field on the growth of the mixing layer thickness and on the production of turbulent kinetic energy.

4.1. The interaction parameter

The main dimensionless parameter that measures the effects of the electric field on the flow under exam is the interaction parameter Ξ defined in Eq. (1). In analogy with the formulation in Ref. [27, 28], this dimensionless number can be readily obtained by normalizing the momentum conservation equation (3). In particular, the acceleration of the flow is normalized by a factor $\rho_r (\Delta U)^2 / \delta_\omega^0$ and the electric body force is assumed proportional to $\epsilon_0 E^{02} / \delta_\omega^0$. In the latter scaling, the reference electric charge density is derived from normalizing the Eq. (10) in the assumption that the divergence of the electric field scales with E^0 / δ_ω^0 . This assumption is appropriate only in electrically sub-saturated conditions where the electric dipole generated around the reacting layer is able to significantly alter the electric potential distribution.

Several conclusions could be drawn by analyzing the definition of the interaction parameter. First of all, it can be shown that sub-breakdown electric fields can induce a modification of flow fields only in low-speed configurations. In fact, it is clear that the intensity of the applied electric field E^0 must grow proportionally to the characteristic flow velocity in order to retain a constant Ξ . However, the dielectric strength of the gas mixture sets an upper bound to the maximum electric field intensity. For this reason, the setup considered in this study involves a very low convective Mach number.

Increasing the operating pressure could enable the application of the electrically controlled combustion in configuration with faster flows without exceeding the electric breakdown of the gas mixture [70]. If the definition of the

reduced electric field is substituted into the interaction parameter definition, it can be shown that

$$\Xi = \epsilon_0 \frac{P_r}{T_a} \frac{N_A}{k_B \bar{W}_r} \left(\frac{E^0}{N_r \Delta U} \right)^2, \quad (22)$$

where N_r and \bar{W}_r are the number density and the mixture reference state. The previous expression demonstrates that Ξ scales linearly with the thermodynamic pressure at a constant reduced electric field. Moreover, a constant interaction parameter could be retained by scaling the thermodynamic pressure with the square of the characteristic velocity scale for given E^0/N_r , T_a , and \bar{W}_r . On one hand, this aspect is encouraging considering that most of the burners for aerospace propulsion and energy production operate at high pressure. On the other hand, the quadratic scaling that relates the density and velocity at a given reduced electric field, interaction parameter, temperature, and chemical composition implies that very high pressure must be achieved to allow a significant increase in the flow velocity.

From a computational point of view, it can be shown that the computational cost of executing a numerical simulation of an electrified flame with an explicit compressible Navier–Stokes solver is proportional to $\mu_e E^0 / [\Delta U + (c_f + c_a) / 2]$. In fact, the maximum time-advancement step sizes set by the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition on the flow fast acoustics and drift velocities scale with the inverse of $[\Delta U + (c_f + c_a) / 2]$ and of $\mu_e E^0$, respectively. Introducing the time step ratio in Eq. (1), it is possible to demonstrate that the computational cost ratio C between the numerical simulation of an electrified and non-electrified flame is

$$C \sim \mu_e \sqrt{\rho_r \Xi / \epsilon_0} / \left(1 + \frac{1}{Ma_c} \right). \quad (23)$$

Considering that the dielectric permittivity of vacuum is $\epsilon_0 = 8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C}/(\text{V m})$, direct numerical simulations of electrified flames are only feasible for moderate interaction parameters and mixture densities. Moreover, the presented estimate of the computational cost ratio neglects the overhead of the Poisson solver required to determine the electrostatic potential, providing an optimistic value of C .

Considering all the described implications of considering an electric field in a direct numerical simulation, the calculations presented in this work are designed at atmospheric pressure and consider $\Xi = 10^{-2}$. This combination of the operating parameters warrants a mild effect of the electrostatic force on the fluid flow but still provides insights into the statistical properties of this interaction at an affordable computational cost.

4.2. Growth of the electrified mixing layer

A quantity that is usually utilized to describe the growth of a temporal mixing layer is the normalized time derivative of the momentum thickness, which can be expressed

as

$$\dot{\delta}_\theta = \frac{1}{\Delta U} \frac{d\delta_\theta}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho_r (\Delta U)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial(\rho \widetilde{u})}{\partial t} dy \quad (24)$$

using Eq. (18). In analogy with the derivation proposed by Vreman [67], $\dot{\delta}_\theta$ can be rewritten using the transport equation of the mean kinetic energy of the flow as

$$\dot{\delta}_\theta = \frac{2}{\rho_r (\Delta U)^3} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \widetilde{u}}{\partial y} \overline{\tau}_{12} dy - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \widetilde{u}}{\partial y} \overline{\rho} \mathcal{R}_{12} dy - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \overline{\widetilde{u} \rho'_q E'_x} dy \right] \quad (25)$$

The first two integrals in the RHS of Eq. (25) are typical of temporal mixing layers. The first integral takes into account the molecular viscosity effects and is usually negligible in completely developed high-Reynolds number flows. The second integral corresponds to the integrated mean turbulent production and is usually the leading order term in Eq. (25) for turbulent mixing layers [67, 68]. The third integral in the RHS Eq. (25) is specific to electrified flows and takes into account the electric body force contribution to the growth of the statistically two-dimensional mixing layer.

Figures 4(a) and (b) show the time-evolution of the Reynolds number based on the instantaneous momentum thickness and the normalized total production of water vapor

$$\dot{W}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \overline{\dot{w}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} dy, \quad (26)$$

which is here retained as an integral measure of the global reaction rate. As discussed in Sec. 4.1, the applied electric field is not able to significantly alter either the growth of the mixing layer or the global reaction rate at both considered Reynolds numbers. The reasons for this inability of the electric field to influence the evolution of the flame are further explainable by analyzing the terms in the RHS of Eq. (25).

Table 2 reports the values of the three terms appearing in the RHS of Eq. (25) evaluated at the end of the two electrified calculations presented in this work. As expected, the mean turbulent production term is dominant and mostly independent of the Reynolds number. In fact, this term determines the linear growth of Re_θ observed in Figure 4(a) for $\delta_\omega^0/\Delta U \gtrsim 200$. The contribution of the viscous term is one order of magnitude lower than that of the turbulent production and approximately scales between the two shear layer states as the inverse of the Reynolds number. The mean contribution of the electric field is definitely the weakest among the three terms. On average, the electric field tends to decrease the mixing layer growth for the specific configuration under exam. However, its integrated contribution is three orders of magnitude lower than the leading order term, therefore this effect is negligible for the conditions under exam. Such disparity of

orders of magnitude is, at a first glance, surprising considering that the chosen interaction parameter is $\Xi = 10^{-2}$. In fact, $\rho'_q E'_x / [\rho_r (\Delta U)^2]$ could be expected to scale with Ξ . Note, that the mean electric field in the x direction is zero because of the periodicity of the chosen configuration, therefore E'_x is only due to the inhomogeneity of the charge density field. The relation between the fluctuations of the electric field and ρ'_q is described by the Poisson equation

$$\epsilon_0 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}' + \rho'_q = 0. \quad (27)$$

The structure of Eq. (27) entails that the largest fluctuations of the electric charge density, which are located inside the mixing layer, will correspond to regions of weak \mathbf{E}' . For this reason, the single point correlation function $\overline{E'_x \rho'_q} / \left(\sqrt{\overline{E_x'^2}} \sqrt{\overline{\rho_q'^2}} \right)$, which is shown in Figure 4(c) as a function of the mixing-normal coordinate and appears in the electric source term for the momentum thickness evolution, is different from zero only inside the mixing layer, where it is anyway very small. The reduced correlation between E'_x and ρ'_q , in conjunction with the low mean streamwise flow velocity observed within the mixing layer, determines the weak contribution of the electric field to the shear layer growth. Future studies will focus on determining the dependence of this result on the intensity and polarity of the applied electric field.

The weak interaction between the electric field and the mean shear layer growth appears to be determined by the structure of the flow itself rather than by the weak intensity of the electric field. This result suggests that this interaction might not be relevant to the hydrodynamics even when stronger electric fields are applied. Clearly, this hypothesis must be verified in the future using calculations with higher interaction parameters.

4.3. Electric production of the turbulent kinetic energy

Another path that the electric field has to influence the flow is through the production of turbulent stresses. In fact, additional electric-field-related terms appear in the conservation equation of the Reynolds stress tensor $\mathcal{R}_{ij} = \overline{u_i'' u_j''}$, which can be derived from the Eq. (3) by applying a Favre decomposition of the velocity field. This equation, which reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\overline{\rho} \mathcal{R}_{ij})}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\overline{\rho} \widetilde{u}_k \mathcal{R}_{ij})}{\partial x_k} &= -\overline{\rho} \left(\mathcal{R}_{ik} \frac{\partial \widetilde{u}_j}{\partial x_k} + \mathcal{R}_{jk} \frac{\partial \widetilde{u}_i}{\partial x_k} \right) \\ &\quad - \overline{\tau'_{jk} \frac{\partial u_i''}{\partial x_k}} - \overline{\tau'_{ik} \frac{\partial u_j''}{\partial x_k}} \\ &\quad - \frac{\overline{\left(\rho u_k'' u_i'' u_j'' + \overline{P' u_i''} \delta_{jk} + \overline{P' u_j''} \delta_{ik} - \tau'_{jk} u_i'' - \tau'_{ik} u_j'' \right)}}{\partial x_k} \\ &\quad + \overline{u_i''} \left(\frac{\partial \overline{\tau}_{jk}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial \overline{P}}{\partial x_j} \right) + \overline{u_j''} \left(\frac{\partial \overline{\tau}_{ik}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial \overline{P}}{\partial x_i} \right) \\ &\quad + \overline{P'} \left(\frac{\partial u_i''}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j''}{\partial x_i} \right) + \overline{\rho_q (E_j u_i'' + E_i u_j'')}, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Figure 4: Evolution of the (a) Reynolds number based on the mixing layer momentum thickness and of the (b) total normalized production of H_2O . (c) One-point correlation between charge density and electric field fluctuations. (d) Electric source term in the streamwise mixing-normal component of the Reynolds stress tensor. The curve $\Xi = 0$ in panels (a) and (b) shows the evolution of the electroneutral simulation.

Label	$\frac{2}{\rho_r (\Delta U)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} \bar{\tau}_{12} dy$	$\frac{2}{\rho_r (\Delta U)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} \bar{\rho} \mathcal{R}_{12} dy$	$\frac{2}{\rho_r (\Delta U)^3} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{u} \overline{\rho_q E_x} dy$
$\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re	2.47×10^{-4}	-2.97×10^{-3}	1.74×10^{-6}
$\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re	1.81×10^{-4}	-3.07×10^{-3}	1.84×10^{-6}

Table 2: Evaluation of the RHS of Eq. (25) at the final stage of the “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re” and “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re” calculations.

has been thoroughly discussed in the context of non-electrified non-reacting mixing layers in Ref. [68, 71]. It is noteworthy that, in the case of electrified flows, the last term on the RHS appears in the equation and takes into account the effects of the electric body force on the velocity fluctuations. This term is active both on the isotropic and deviatoric parts of the Reynolds stress tensor. For instance, the normalized electric source term for \mathcal{R}_{12} is shown in Figure 4(d). This term is expected to be one of the most active in the configuration under exam because it involves the product of two of the strongest components of the elec-

tric body force and the Favre fluctuations of velocity. In particular, these components are the electric body force that acts along the y -direction and the streamwise velocity fluctuations. As it will be discussed in Sec. 5.2, the $\rho_q E_y$ is the strongest component of the electric body force but is active mostly outside the mixing layer. Conversely, the velocity fluctuations are mainly located inside the mixing layer, where the shear of the flow sustains turbulence. For this reason, the average product of these two quantities is non-zero only at the edges of the mixing layer, where the profiles of $\rho_q E_y$ and u_x'' overlap, and remains negligible for

the evolution of the flow. An analysis of the other elements of the electric source term in the Eq. (28) would lead to similar conclusions, therefore is omitted.

Considering that the weakness of the electric field effects on the Reynolds stress tensor is again mostly due to the structure of the flow rather than to the intensity of the electric body force, it could be hypothesized that similar observations could be drawn for flows at stronger interaction parameters. Further investigations are required on this aspect.

5. Statistical properties of the electric quantities

Even if the electric body force is not capable of modifying the hydrodynamic field of the flow under exam, a thorough characterization of the statistical properties of the electric quantities of the flow is still useful to guide the formulation of new combustion models that take into account the ion-wind effects generated by external electric fields. For this reason, this section discusses i) the analysis of the electric charge density field and its effects on the electric potential field, ii) the distribution of the electrically charged species that contribute the aforementioned ρ_q field, and iii) the electric body force field arisen from the imposed electric field.

5.1. Electric charge density and electric field

Figures 5(a) and (b) show the distribution of the mean and RMS of the normalized electric charge density across the mixing layer. On average, the turbulent flame produces an electric dipole similar to what has been observed for laminar sub-saturated counterflow diffusion flames [27–29]. Positive and negative ions tend to accumulate at the edge of the thermal mixing layer, whereby the number of collisions between the charged particles and the neutral species increases. Similarly, moving away from the mixing layer, the mean electric charge tends to decrease as a consequence of the increase in the mean electric field observed in Figure 5(c). The electric charge fluctuation distribution is characterized by a dual-peak shape. The positions of the two peaks correspond to those of the $\bar{\rho}_q$. At these locations, the electric charge is maximum and the turbulent mixing is also very active, as shown by the RMS of density in Figure 2(d). While the momentum thickness appears to be the right scaling to collapse the mixing normal coordinates of these electric charge density profiles, the normalization utilized for the ρ_q is not appropriate. In fact, both the mean and RMS profiles of the higher Reynolds number state are scaled by a factor of 1.5 with respect to “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re”. This factor is equal to the ratio of the vorticity thicknesses of the two mixing layer states. For this reason, we can conclude that the vorticity thickness is not an appropriate length scale for constructing the normalization of the electric charge density field and further investigation will be required in the future to identify a better normalization factor.

Figures 5(c) and (d) show the mean and RMS distributions of the normalized electric field across the mixing layer. The mean electric field shows a minimum around the reacting layer of the flame, which is the consequence of the dielectric dipole described in Figure 5(a). As commonly observed in laminar electrified flames, the ionized species form a sort of Faraday cage around the reacting layer [20, 21, 27, 29]. The fluctuations of the electric field in all three directions show a dual-peak shape, whereby the two fluctuations peaks are located on both sides of the flame. However, the amplitude of these fluctuations in the three Cartesian directions is three orders of magnitude lower on average than the mean electric field. As discussed later in this section, the lower intensity of the electric field fluctuations is mainly the result of the filtering nature of the Laplace operator that appears in the Gauss law, which dampens the effects of short-scale electric charge density oscillations. It is noteworthy that neither the mean nor the RMS profiles of the two considered mixing layer states are well-collapsed by the utilized scaling. Further study will be required to understand the intrinsic reasons for this failure and to formulate a better normalization of the electric field intensity.

Figures 6(a) and (b) provide instantaneous visualizations of the normalized temperature and charge density fields obtained for the “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re” state. When comparing these two figures, it appears clear how the peaks of positive/negative charge density are formed on the upper/lower side of the diffusion flame that is corrugated and strained by the turbulence. The peaks are elongated by the electric field toward free streams, where clear footprints of electric charge inhomogeneity are still evident. Such a distribution of ρ_q is characterized by a broad power spectrum when it is Fourier-transformed in the streamwise and spanwise directions. In fact, Figure 6(c) shows that the normalized power spectrum of the electric charge density is very broad in the region of the mixing layer, where the non-linear interaction of turbulence and chemistry generated a lot of small-scale features in the ρ_q field. The spectrum becomes much narrower in the fuel and oxidizer streams, where mass and electric diffusion tend to create a more uniform ρ_q distribution. The filtering properties of the Laplace operator inbuilt into the Gauss law entail a very narrow power spectrum of the electric potential field, which is mostly uniform in the homogeneous directions as also shown by the isolines in Figure 6(b) and has mild oscillations within the mixing layer. If we consider Eq. (10) transformed in the Fourier space along the x and z directions, it can be shown that

$$\frac{d^2 \hat{\Phi}}{d^2 y} = (k_x^2 + k_z^2) \hat{\Phi} - \frac{\hat{\rho}_q}{\epsilon_0}, \quad (29)$$

where k_x and k_z are the wavenumbers in the x and z directions and $\hat{\cdot}$ means that the quantity has been transformed in Fourier space. The first term on the RHS tends to dampen the higher frequency content of Φ , while the

Figure 5: Distribution of the (a) mean and (b) RMS of the normalized electric charge density. Distribution of (c) the mean normalized electric field component in the mixing normal direction and of (d) the normalized electric field fluctuation throughout the mixing layer. The black dotted and dot-dashed lines in the four panels show the location of the mean stoichiometric mixture in the red dashed line in “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re” and “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re” cases, respectively.

second term introduces the perturbations due to the local electric charge density. At the edge of the mixing layer, where the Faraday cage effect is observed, the term $\widehat{\rho}_q/\epsilon_0$ is significant and generates fluctuations in the electric potential field. As shown in Figure 5(b), in this configuration, the ρ'_q are higher on the fuel side than on the oxidizer side, where they generate less intense fluctuations of Φ . For this reason, Figure 6(d) is asymmetric with respect to the mixing layer. The fluctuations of ρ_q are much less intense away from the mixing layer and become negligible in the Eq. (29). For this reason, the values of $\widehat{\Phi}$ remain mostly constant for low wave numbers and dampened in their higher frequencies while propagating in the y direction.

5.2. Electric body force field

The mean profiles of the normalized electric body force and of its fluctuations are provided in Figure 7. As a result of the electro-neutral region developed by the electric charge peaks described in the previous section, the mean electric body force is zero in the proximity of the flame. Having a negligible electric body force at the location of the higher strain of the flow is the main reason for the decoupling of the turbulence from the electric body force. The electric body force ramps up at the edges of the mixing layer because of the increase in electric charge density and of the electric field until it reaches a constant value outside the mixing layer, whereby the total ion-flux is constant due to the conservation of charges. In fact, Han *et al.* [17] analytically showed that the electric body force is proportional to the local ion flux divided by the effec-

Figure 6: Contour plots of an instantaneous $x - y$ plane visualization of (a) the normalized temperature and (b) charge density at the final state of the “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re” calculation. The white arrows in panel (a) show the direction of the mean fuel and air flows while the iso-electric potential lines are plotted in black in panel (b) and labeled with the corresponding fraction of the applied voltage $-E^0 L_y$. Two-dimensional power spectra across the domain for the electric charge density (c) and potential (d). The red dashed line in panels (c, d) shows the average location of the stoichiometric mixture fraction line.

tive electric mobility of the ions. The ionic composition of the mixture outside the mixing layer is mostly constant, as shown in Figure 8. For this reason, the effective mobility of ions does not change outside of the mixing layer on either side of the flame. This aspect of the ion transport, in conjunction with the charge conservation principle which imposes that the mean total ion flux is constant outside of the reacting layer of the flame, explains the distribution of the electric body force in the computational domain.

Similarly to the ρ_q field and electric field, the electric body force fluctuations show a two-peak distribution. The fluctuations in the streamwise and spanwise directions are one order of magnitude lower than those in the mixing-normal direction. While the electric body force in the periodic directions is only generated by the concurrent presence of electric charge and electric field fluctuations, the fluctuations in the electric body force in the y direction are also generated by the product of the mean electric

field with the electric charge density. A byproduct of the disparity of intensity between the electric body force fluctuations along the three Cartesian directions is that the electric body force remains mostly aligned in the direction of the mean electric field. This aspect could be useful for the formulation of turbulence sub-grid scale closure models for electrified flames when neither the electric potential nor the electric charge fields will be fully described by the computational grid.

5.3. Charged species

The mean and RMS distributions of the charged species molar fractions across the mixing layer are shown for the two analyzed states in Figure 8. In both analyzed conditions, the concentration of CHO^+ is three orders of magnitude lower than all the other species. This result, which was already observed in previous studies about laminar

Figure 7: Distribution of the (a) mean and (b) RMS of the normalized electric body force. The black dotted and dot-dashed lines in the four panels show the location of the mean stoichiometric mixture in the “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re” and “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re” cases, respectively.

Figure 8: Distribution of the charged species (a) mean and (b) RMS molar fraction profiles. The continuous and the dashed lines correspond to the results computed at the “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ lo-Re” and “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re” states, respectively.

electrified flames, is the consequence of the short time scale associated with the charge transfer reaction

which happens almost instantaneously compared to the other chemi-ionization and recombination processes. The molar fractions of H_3O^+ and e^- are equal on average within the reacting layer of the flame, where the gas mixture is electrically neutral. Because of the applied electric field, a portion of the H_3O^+ molecules escapes the reacting layer toward the fuel side. Similarly, the free electrons drift toward the oxidizer side where, upon collision with the molecular oxygen, are completely transformed into O_2^- , which then flows toward the positive electrode. Such an electron attachment process is fundamental to ensure that

similar intensities of the electric body force are exerted on the fluid on both sides of the mixing layer. In fact, O_2^- has much lower electric mobility compared to the free electrons. For this reason, if free electrons were able to escape the reacting layer without combining with any other heavy particles, as would happen with an applied electric field with opposite polarity, they would produce a much weaker Lorentz force on the fluid.

The charged species molar fractions RMS show profiles across the mixing layer that are very similar to the mean profiles counterparts. It is noteworthy that these RMS are of the same order of magnitude as the mean values, indicating strong intermittency of the charged species concentration fields. This strong intermittency is the source of the electric charge fluctuations shown in Figure 5(b).

In a large eddy or Reynolds-averaged simulation, most of these fluctuations will happen at length scales that are not captured by the computational grid, therefore future turbulence closure models will need to face the challenging problem of predicting these oscillations, which are ultimately the main source of the electric body force RMS shown in Figure 7(b).

Consistently with the electric charge profiles in Figures 5(a) and (b), the charged species molar fraction profiles seem to be well-scaled by the momentum thickness of the mixing layer. The profiles of the presented statistics for the two states are coincident for most of the species across the entire computational domain. The major difference between the analyzed states is observed in the mean profiles of O_2^- molar fractions inside the reacting layer. A lower concentration of oxide is observed in the higher Reynolds number case, whereby the molecular oxygen field is more intermittent. A similar trend between the two mixing layer states is observed for the oxide RMS profiles, though the decrease of this quantity within this mixing layer is less pronounced than in the mean profiles.

5.4. Alignment of the electric field and mixture fraction gradient

One class of turbulent combustion models that are commonly utilized to predict turbulent flames in industrial configurations is the FPV model [72–74]. In this type of model, the chemistry is described in a low-dimensional manifold, whereby the mixing process between the fuel and oxidizer is described by the mixture fraction field. During the formulation of these models for the prediction of electrified flames, it would be desirable to project the charged species transport within the mixture fraction space and reduce the number of quantities to be transported during the numerical simulation. One of the main parameters that control the accuracy of the projections is the alignment of the electric field with the mixture fraction gradient.

Figure 9 plots the probability density function, and its first statistical moment, of the absolute value of the normalized dot product of the mixture fraction gradient and electric field. From a modeling perspective, it would be desirable to observe a $|\nabla Z \cdot \mathbf{E}| / (|\nabla Z| |\mathbf{E}|)$ as close as possible to one. The data shown in the figure highlight that the electric field is often not aligned with the mixture fraction gradient. In particular, the mean value of the normalized dot product between the electric field and the mixture fraction gradient is about 0.6 throughout the entire mixing layer for both the Reynolds numbers considered in this study. Within the mixing layer ($0.05 \leq \tilde{Z} \leq 0.8$), the probability density function shown in Figure 9(b) peaks at $|\nabla Z \cdot \mathbf{E}| / (|\nabla Z| |\mathbf{E}|) \sim 1$ with values close to 1.5. However, the distribution remains mostly flat with minimum values close to 0.8. At the same time, the probability density function does not show any preferential value of $|\nabla Z \cdot \mathbf{E}| / (|\nabla Z| |\mathbf{E}|)$ at the edges of the mixing layer, including where the stoichiometric mixture is present.

These results highlight significant challenges in the sub-grid scale modeling of turbulent electrified flames. The presence of electric fields that are not aligned with the mixture fraction gradient entails the appearance of electric drift fluxes of the electrically charged species that cannot be described within a mixture fraction space framework. Moreover, the lack of preferential alignment between the mixing and the electric field will also induce difficulties in closing the unresolved ion-wind fluxes.

6. Conclusions

A turbulent methane/air diffusion flame impinged by an external electric field is studied in this work using direct numerical simulations. The flow under exam is a temporally evolving mixing layer, whereby two streams at 1 atm and composed of air and of a mixture of methane and nitrogen flow in opposite directions at a Reynolds number that is sufficiently high to trigger the formation and sustained turbulence. A diffusion flame with a stoichiometric mixture fraction $Z_{st} = 0.2$ is formed within the mixing layer and produces, as a byproduct, a number of electrically charged species. The external electric field is oriented in the direction normal to the mean mixing plane and steers the positive and negative ions in opposite directions generating an ion-wind.

The interaction parameter considered in this study has been kept to moderate values to palliate the calculations' computational cost. For this reason, a strong influence of the electric body force on hydrodynamics was not expected. However, the effective source terms encountered in the evolution equation of the mixing layer momentum thickness and of the Reynolds stresses are several orders of magnitude lower than foreseen by the scaling analysis. Such a discrepancy is mainly due to the structure of the electrified flame. In fact, the electric body forces are developed outside the thermal and momentum mixing layer, whereby the temperature drops, the density increases, and the ions undergo a larger number of collisions driven by their electric drift. On the other hand, the mixing layer growth is mainly governed by the turbulent mixing happening within the shear layer. These results suggest that the weakness of the interaction between the electric body force and the turbulence is dictated by the structure of the analyzed flow rather than the intensity of the applied voltage. Further studies at higher interaction parameters will be required in the future to corroborate or reject this hypothesis.

Though the influence of the electric field on the flow is weak, a strong one-way coupling between the turbulence and the electric quantities is observed. Strong fluctuations of the mean electric quantities, such as the electric charge density and the ions concentration fields, have been observed. These fluctuations are characterized by very short length scales, can be as intense as the local mean value of the quantity, and are relevant for the correct prediction of the electric response of the flame. Future sub-grid

Figure 9: (a) Distribution and (b) probability density function of the absolute value of the normalized dot product between the mixture fraction gradient and the electric field in the mixing layer. The probability density function is constructed for the case “ $\Xi = 10^{-2}$ hi-Re”.

scale models will need to take into account the presence of these fluctuations, which most likely will be marginally captured at the grid resolution utilized in large-eddy or Reynolds-averaged simulations. On the other hand, the filtering nature of the Laplace operator contained in the Gauss law determines a very small spectral content for the electric potential field, which will be easily well-captured by coarser grids. Moreover, the electric field, and consequently the electric body force, remain mostly aligned with the external electrostatic field, strongly simplifying the complexity of determining the direction of sub-grid scale electric body forces.

The response of the analyzed turbulent flow is reminiscent of the behavior of electrified laminar diffusion flames [27–29]. For instance, both types of diffusion flames are able, on average, to produce a strong electric dipole that isolates the reacting layer of the flame from the applied electric field. Moreover, if the voltage polarity induces a drift of the free electrons toward the oxidizer side of turbulent and laminar flames, the ion wind is composed of heavy ions. For this reason, the electric body force is similar on both sides of these flames. Finally, [28] observed that a hydrodynamic effect of the electric body force for a laminar counterflow diffusion flame was only possible because of the rotational components of the body force. The observations made in Section 4.2 may suggest that this property holds also for turbulent flames and that configurations with two or three-dimensional mean flow are necessary to observe a mean effect of the applied electric field on the hydrodynamics. However, further studies, involving different voltage polarities and intensities, are required to confirm this hypothesis.

Other exciting challenges emerged with respect to determining whether the electrified reacting mixing layer re-

tains some degree of self-similarity. In this respect, the momentum thickness of the boundary layer appeared to be a very solid scaling to collapse most of the quantities related to the hydrodynamics and neutral chemistry. On the other hand, the collapse of the electric quantities, particularly of the electric field, proved particularly challenging. Considering the potential benefit of knowing an appropriate scaling for the quantities of interest during the definition of future sub-grid scale models, additional work is required to understand the reasons behind this lack of collapse in the electric field developed by the flow and identify appropriate corrections.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 898458. The first author acknowledges the computational resources provided by US Department of Energy, National Nuclear Security Administration under Award Number DE-NA0003968 within the PSAAP III (INSIEME) Center at Stanford University. The authors are also grateful to the reviewers of this manuscript for their constructive and insightful comments.

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